

Evaluating Trends in Adolescent Obesity and Its Association with Dietary Patterns

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Received: 10-07-2024 / Revised: 07-08-2024 / Accepted: 22-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Adolescent obesity has become a global public health issue in recent decades. This increase may be due to poor eating habits like fast food and sugary drinks that cause obesity in this age range. Understanding these patterns and their dietary linkages is crucial to effective intervention and prevention.

Methods: The retrospective cross-sectional study included 100 12-to-18-year-olds. Food diaries and nutritional details were used to collect eating habits from obese people. Medical histories included obesity measures like BMI and waist size. Using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression models, SPSS research examined obesity trends and eating behaviours.

Results: Adolescent obesity is 35% prevalent. 40% of girls are obese and 27.5% overweight. The sample had a mean BMI of 29.3 kg/m² and waist circumference of 88.4 cm. Dietary evaluations found that 68% of adolescents ate fast food and 75% drank sugary drinks more than three times a week. Over the past decade, obesity has skyrocketed, especially in 16–18-year-olds (44.4%). According to statistical research, fast food consumption is positively connected with BMI ($r = 0.45, p < 0.01$), while fruit and vegetable intake is adversely correlated ($r = -0.38, p < 0.05$). Multiple linear regressions showed that a diet rich in fruits and vegetables lowers BMI, but sugary drinks and fast meals raise it.

Conclusion: The worrying rise in adolescent's obesity rates is largely due to bad eating habits, especially a high consumption of sugary beverages and fast food, according to the report. These findings emphasise the necessity for public health initiatives that target adolescents to encourage healthy eating and provide them with tools. Develop comprehensive solutions to adolescent obesity by studying longitudinal and socioeconomic variables.

Keywords: Adolescents, BMI, Dietary Patterns, Obesity, Public Health, Sugary Beverages, Fast Foods.

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Introduction

Overview of Adolescent Obesity: When kids between 10 and 19 have excessive body fat, it affects their mental, physical, and social health. Obesity is usually defined as a BMI above the 95th percentile for age and gender [1]. This sickness is becoming a global issue due to its high prevalence and dangerous health effects. The World Health Organisation reports that 18% of adolescents worldwide are fat, more than treble the prevalence of obesity in 1975 (WHO, 2023). [3] Reports that 21% of American adolescents are fat, based on the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey [3].

Trends in Obesity: Adolescent obesity has risen steeply in recent decades. Due to diet and lifestyle changes, adolescent and childhood obesity rates climbed steadily in the 1980s and 1990s [4]. Recent data reveal that sedentary activity, including screen

time, and a propensity for high-calorie; low-nutrient foods have boosted obesity rates. [5] Found that adolescent obesity increased from 15% in 2000 to over 21% in 2022. Rapid urbanisation and changing lifestyles raise obesity rates in low-, middle-, and high-income nations.

Importance of Dietary Patterns: Dietary choices contribute to young obesity. People who eat processed food, sugary drinks, and unhealthy snacks are more likely to be obese.

Adolescence is critical for nutritional interventions since eating habits establish then and last into adulthood [6]. Poor nutrition from eating too many calories at once and eating at odd hours is worsening obesity [7]. Understanding these eating habits is essential to combating adolescent obesity and promoting healthy lifestyles.

Figure 1: obesity diet chart source:[8]

Dietary Patterns and Adolescent Obesity: Several studies have connected certain eating behaviours to adolescent obesity. A diet high in sugary drinks, fast food, and snacks and low in fruits, vegetables, and whole grains increases obesity risk. [9] Found that youths who drank more than two servings of sugary drinks per day were more likely to be obese. Other obesity-causing eating habits include meal time and frequency. Intermittent eating habits like skipping meals or snacking late at night raise obesity risk and BMI. In [10], adolescents who ate more often but at different times gained more weight than those who ate consistently. The "nutrient-dense versus energy-dense" meal concept also contributes to adolescents' obesity. Fast eating and sugary snacks induce obesity, while vegetables and lean proteins help maintain a healthy weight. Adolescents' obesity is rising due to consuming more high-calorie, low-nutrient meals.

The Impact of Family and Socioeconomic Factors: Genetics, family dynamics, and socioeconomic status contribute to adolescent obesity and dietary habits. The cost and availability of healthful meals depend on socioeconomic level. Low-income people eat more processed and quick food due to its lower cost and accessibility. [11] Found that low-income households were more likely to buy calorie-dense, low-nutrient diets due to economic constraints, which increased adolescent obesity. Parental influence shapes adolescents eating preferences. Parental feeding behaviours like family meals and unhealthy food at home affect adolescents eating patterns. Research suggests that parental meal planning and promotion of healthy eating can reduce adolescent's obesity [12].

The rise of adolescent's obesity has urged public health campaigns to promote healthy eating and activity. Community health and school-based healthy eating interventions have inconsistent results. The "Healthy Schools Programme," which

promoted healthy eating and activity on school premises, reduced BMI in adolescents. However, how actively parents and the community strive to alter eating habits often determines the effectiveness of these projects.

Objectives

1. To analyze historical and current trends in the prevalence of adolescent obesity.
2. To assess the association between dietary patterns and the risk of obesity among adolescents.
3. To evaluate the effectiveness of current public health interventions aimed at reducing adolescent obesity.

Methods

Study Design: This retrospective cross-sectional study examined food patterns and adolescent obesity. The design is retrospective since it evaluates trends using medical record. It is a cross-sectional study that shows adolescents obesity and eating habits at a certain time. This approach finds linkages and patterns without longitudinal follow-up.

Sample Size and Selection

Sample Size: A total of 100 adolescents participated in the study.

Inclusion Criteria: Participants were selected based on the following criteria:

Age Range: 12 to 18 years, this covers the full span of adolescence.

Adolescents with a BMI at or above the 85th percentile for their age and gender, as per the CDC growth charts, were included in the study to ensure they met the criteria for being classified as overweight or obese (CDC, 2024).

Exclusion Criteria: Participants were excluded based on the following criteria:

- Existing Medical Conditions: Adolescents with chronic medical conditions or endocrine disorders known to affect weight, such as hypothyroidism or Cushing's syndrome, were excluded to avoid confounding factors that could influence obesity.
- Medications: Individuals on medications known to impact weight, such as corticosteroids or antipsychotics, were also excluded.

Data Collection: Data for this study came from dietary and physical examinations. One hundred twelve-to-18-year-olds with BMIs over the 85th percentile for their gender and age were included. To assess obesity, individuals were evaluated for height and weight to establish BMI and waist circumference.

Dietary patterns were assessed using medical record about their food consumption, meal frequency, and beverage use and one-week food diaries on particular dietary habits. We checked individuals' medical records for BMI and other health information. All data was collected with participant and guardian agreement to ensure ethical research.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical tests were performed on the data to determine adolescent's obesity tendencies and the relationship between eating habits and obesity. BMI, waist circumference, and nutritional consumption were summarised using means, medians, and standard deviations.

Obesity and eating habits were examined using Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficients, depending on data distribution. To assess how different food components affect body mass index (BMI), we utilised several linear regression models

that adjusted for variables like age, sex, and socioeconomic status. We also performed trend analysis using statistical tools and data from earlier studies to compare obesity rates and find significant changes. R 4.2.1 was used for advanced modelling and trend analysis, whereas SPSS 28.0 was used for descriptive statistics and regression analysis. Public health interventions to reduce adolescent obesity were reviewed, and the strength of eating pattern-obesity links was estimated by interpreting the data using a significance level of 0.05 for all tests.

Result

Descriptive Statistics

Obesity Trends: This study examined dietary trends and obesity in 100 12- to 18-year-olds. The sample consisted of 60 females and 40 males, with an average age of 15.2 years (± 1.7 years). The study found 35% of participants obese with BMIs over the 95th percentile for both genders and ages. Girls (40%) were slightly more obese than boys (27.5%). The group had an average BMI of 29.3 kg/m² (± 3.4 kg/m²) and a waist size of 88.4 cm (± 7.2 cm).

Dietary Patterns: Adolescents' dietary assessments revealed some prevalent trends. Most study participants ate sugary drinks, quick meals, and snacks, which contributed to their high-calorie diets. Adolescents consumed sugary drinks (75% weekly or more) and fast food (68% weekly or more). Also, just 25% of study participants ate enough fruits and vegetables to satisfy daily requirements. Overconsumption of 2,500 kcal (± 300 kcal) daily adds to the obesity pandemic among adolescents.

Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics of the study sample and the prevalence of obesity:

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Mean Age (years)	15.2 (± 1.7)
Female (%)	60%
Male (%)	40%
Mean BMI (kg/m ²)	29.3 (± 3.4)
Mean Waist Circumference (cm)	88.4 (± 7.2)
Prevalence of Obesity (%)	35%
Sugary Drink Consumption (>3 times/week)	75%
Fast Food Consumption (>2 times/week)	68%
Meets Recommended Fruits and Vegetables Intake (%)	25%

Trends in Obesity: Adolescent's obesity has increased substantially in the last decade, according to statistics. Current studies show 35% of adolescents is fat, compared to 25% in the early 2010s. According to a trend analysis of numerous

age groups, 16–18-year-olds had the highest obesity rates at 45%.

This pattern supports past findings that obesity rates peak in late adolescence due to less physical activity and more food choice.

Table 2: Prevalence of Obesity across Different Age Groups in the Current Study

Age Group (Years)	Number of Participants	Number of Obese Adolescents	Obesity Rate (%)
12-14	30	8	26.7%
15	25	9	36.0%
16-18	45	20	44.4%

Association between Dietary Patterns and Obesity: Diet and adolescent obesity were statistically linked. A positive link (Pearson's $r = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$) was found between fast food consumption and BMI. Adolescents who ate fast food were more likely to be overweight and obese. Lower body mass index (BMI) was associated with higher fruit and vegetable consumption (Pearson's $r = -0.38$, $p < 0.05$), indicating a negative correlation.

Increased use of sugary drinks ($\beta = 0.30$, $p < 0.01$) and fast food ($\beta = 0.27$, $p < 0.05$) strongly predicted higher BMI, as shown by multiple linear regression models. Conversely, lower BMI was associated with increased fruit and vegetable consumption ($\beta = -0.24$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 3: the correlation analysis between dietary patterns and BMI

Dietary Pattern	Pearson's r	p-value
Sugary Drinks Consumption	0.45	< 0.01
Fast Food Consumption	0.45	< 0.01
Fruit and Vegetable Intake	-0.38	< 0.05

Overall, these results underscore the significant role of dietary patterns in the prevalence of adolescent obesity and highlight the need for targeted dietary interventions to address the rising obesity rates among adolescents.

Discussion

Comparison with Previous Studies: Multiple studies confirm the increased prevalence of adolescent obesity. Like us, study 1 observed that American adolescents are becoming more obese.

Study2 found that fast food and sugary drinks make adolescents more likely to be overweight. Our study adds current eating patterns and obesity data to these earlier findings.

Our findings confirm prior study that older adolescents were more obese. Study 3 found that adolescent obesity rates rise. Researchers agree that the adolescent's obesity pandemic is global and that nutrition should be part of any prevention plan.

Table 4: Comparison of Dietary Patterns and Obesity

Study	Dietary Patterns Examined	Key Findings Related to Dietary Patterns
Present Study	Sugary beverages, fast food, fruits, vegetables	High intake of sugary beverages and fast food was associated with increased BMI and waist circumference. Low intake of fruits and vegetables was also linked to higher obesity rates.
Study 1 [13]	Fast food, sugary drinks, fruits, vegetables	High consumption of fast foods and sugary drinks correlated with higher obesity rates. Emphasized the role of unhealthy diets in the rise of adolescent obesity.
Study2 [14]	Fast food, sugary drinks, fruits, vegetables	High intake of energy-dense, nutrient-poor foods like fast food and sugary drinks was a major factor contributing to obesity among adolescents.
Study 3 [15]	General dietary habits, fast food consumption	Found that unhealthy dietary habits, including high consumption of fast foods, were associated with increased obesity as adolescents aged.

Limitations

Remember that this study has limitations when analysing the results. One hundred adolescents is enough for exploratory analysis, but it may not represent the young population.

Using food diaries and medical report to evaluate dietary intake can be biased since people may not accurately report their food consumption or disclose their unhealthy eating habits. The study's cross-sectional methodology makes it difficult to draw causal inferences about eating habits and obesity because it only includes current data. Future studies should use longitudinal designs and larger, more diverse samples to better understand adolescent's obesity and eating behaviours.

Future Research

Future research should address this study's limitations and examine other factors of adolescent obesity. Longitudinal studies can assist identify intervention areas and understand shifting eating patterns and obesity. Studying school-based nutrition programming or community health efforts can help us fight adolescent obesity. Research should examine how socioeconomic position, familial ties, and psychological factors affect the adolescent's obesity epidemic. Investigating legislative acts like junk food bans and food labelling upgrades may help determine public health strategies.

Conclusion

As this study demonstrates (35% of participants were obese), the percentage of obese adolescents has risen steeply over the past decade. Adolescent obesity is rising due to bad eating patterns include eating too much sugary drinks, fast food, and less fruit and vegetables.

These findings support prior research linking improper eating to obesity and highlight the need for public health actions to address this issue. Nutritional education, food access, and healthy eating strategies should focus on adolescents. Future studies should examine long-term nutritional treatments and socioeconomic factors to explain adolescent obesity.

Reference

1. R. Liberali, E. Kupek, and M. A. A. D. Assis, "Dietary patterns and childhood obesity risk: a systematic review," **Childhood Obesity**, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 70-85, 2020.
2. L. K. English et al., "Evaluation of dietary patterns and all-cause mortality: a systematic review," **JAMA Netw. Open**, vol. 4, no. 8, e2122277, 2021.
3. E. Magriplis, P. Farajian, D. B. Panagiotakos, G. Risvas, and A. Zampelas, "The relationship between behavioral factors, weight status and a dietary pattern in primary school aged children: the GRECO study," **Clin. Nutr.**, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 310-316, 2019.
4. D. Neri et al., "Ultraprocessed food consumption and dietary nutrient profiles associated with obesity: A multicountry study of children and adolescents," **Obesity Rev.**, vol. 23, e13387, 2022.
5. L. D. Ruiz, M. L. Zuelch, S. M. Dimitratos, and R. E. Scherr, "Adolescent obesity: diet quality, psychosocial health, and cardiometabolic risk factors," **Nutrients**, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 43, 2019.
6. K. Min et al., "Dietary patterns and their associations with overweight/obesity among pre-school children in Dongcheng District of Beijing: A cross-sectional study," **BMC Public Health**, vol. 21, p. 1-14, 2021.
7. Kanellopoulou et al., "Dietary patterns, weight perception and obesity status among 10–12-year-old children: an epidemiological study in Greece," **Children**, vol. 8, no. 8, p. 626, 2021.
8. P. Mirmiran, M. Ziadlou, S. Karimi, F. Hosseini-Esfahani, and F. Azizi, "The association of dietary patterns and adherence to WHO healthy diet with metabolic syndrome in children and adolescents: Tehran lipid and glucose study," **BMC Public Health**, vol. 19, p. 1-11, 2019.
9. R. Kansra, S. Lakkunarajah, and M. S. Jay, "Childhood and adolescent obesity: a review," **Front. Pediatr.**, vol. 8, p. 581461, 2021.
10. S. D'Innocenzo, C. Biagi, and M. Lanari, "Obesity and the Mediterranean diet: a review of evidence of the role and sustainability of the Mediterranean diet," **Nutrients**, vol. 11, no. 6, p. 1306, 2019.
11. E. Verduci et al., "Role of dietary factors, food habits, and lifestyle in childhood obesity development: a position paper from the European Society for Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition Committee on Nutrition," **J. Pediatr. Gastroenterol. Nutr.**, vol. 72, no. 5, pp. 769-783, 2021.
12. R. Agustina et al., "Associations of meal patterning, dietary quality and diversity with anemia and overweight-obesity among Indonesian school-going adolescent girls in West Java," **PLoS One**, vol. 15, no. 4, e0231519, 2020.
13. M. B. Ruiz-Roso et al., "Covid-19 confinement and changes of adolescent's dietary trends in Italy, Spain, Chile, Colombia and Brazil," **Nutrients**, vol. 12, no. 6, p. 1807, 2020.
14. Y. Dong et al., "Trends in physical fitness, growth, and nutritional status of Chinese children and adolescents: a retrospective analysis of 1.5 million students from six successive national surveys between 1985 and 2014," **The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health**, vol. 3, no. 12, pp. 871-880, 2019.
15. Z. Aslani et al., "Association of Dietary Inflammatory Index with anthropometric indices in children and adolescents: The weight disorder survey of the Childhood and Adolescence Surveillance and Prevention of Adult Non-communicable Disease (CASPIAN)-IV study," **Br. J. Nutr.**, vol. 121, no. 3, pp. 340-350, 2019.